

STRUCTURAL RESPONSE OF BALLISTICALLY DAMAGED COMPOSITE HONEYCOMB SANDWICH STRUCTURES UNDER MULTIPLE BALLISTIC IMPACTS

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Keywords: Composite structures, Ballistic impact, Damage assessment, Structural response

ABSTRACT

This paper presents the effect of multiple ballistic impacts on the structural performance of composite honeycomb sandwich panels. Carbon fibre reinforced plastic and the Nomex honeycomb core were utilised to manufacture the sandwich specimen. Three different projectile calibres were fired to conduct ballistic impact tests in a shooting range. Damage inflicted by small weapons and anti-aircraft ammunition fragments were simulated by firing live (multiple) projectiles into the sandwich specimens. The non-intrusive techniques such as an optical microscopy, X-ray inspections, and computed tomography techniques have been applied to analyse the degree and patterns of damage. In-plane edgewise compression tests were conducted to investigate the structural performance of the intact and ballistically damaged panels. The reduction in the load-resistance ability caused by the multiple ballistic damage has been assessed for the panels under consideration and compared with intact sandwich panels.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre reinforced sandwich structures are increasingly used in aerospace applications for defence and commercial purposes due to their high strength to weight ratios. These structural components have robustness in their design and provide high structural reliability, and their load-resistance capacity makes them predominantly attractive in the aerospace applications. During their service life, these structural components are susceptible to the high-velocity impact loadings with the projectiles originating from space debris, explosive devices, small weapons, etc. The effects of impact loading on the composite structures have been studied in the books published by Vasiliev and Morozov [1] and Hazell [2]. A lot of studies have been conducted on the fibre reinforced composite structures subjected to high velocity impact and a review on the assessment of perforations, perforation process and mechanisms is published by Kasano [3]. Impact resistance, perforations and damage inflicted by ballistic impacts was discussed by Buitrago et al. [4]. It was concluded that the impact load is primarily resisted by the composite facesheets and core had minimal effect on the projectile resistance. The susceptibility of polymer structural components to impact from various projectiles are extensively investigated recently. A review of research findings on the ballistic response of composite materials was reported by Hazell and Appleby-Thomas [5]. The study discussed the impact response of composite materials when subjected to high velocity impact i.e. up to 2 km/s with most of the publications reporting the velocity range of 300 m/s to 1000 m/s. The article reported that thin carbon fibre reinforced composite laminates were not suitable as protection materials from high-velocity projectiles. The effect of fibre type and stacking sequence, temperature effects on the impact resistance, perforations and damage mechanisms were also discussed for glass fibre reinforced composite laminates. A lot of studies on the ballistic impact response of the carbon fibre reinforced structures are mainly focused on the spherical projectiles and not many studies have investigated the effect of live projectiles (i.e. bullets). For instance, Sun et al. [6] have investigated the impact resistance of honeycomb sandwich structures with thin face-sheets. Spherical projectiles of diameter 11.97 mm and mass 7.165 g were used to conduct the ballistic tests with impact velocities ranging from 70 to 170 m/s. The effects of face-sheet thickness, core height, cell wall thickness and

cell size of honeycomb on the impact behaviour of sandwich panels were investigated. The experimental and numerical study of the medium velocity impact response of sandwich panels with different cores was reported by Wang et al. [7]. They tested sandwich specimens of 150×150mm composed of thin aluminium face-sheets with five different cores (i.e., low-density balsa wood, high-density balsa wood, cork, polypropylene honeycomb, and polystyrene foam). The impact loadings were conducted utilising an instrumented vertical gas gun with a spherical impactor of diameter 20mm and a mass of 384.4g. The impact energy ranged from 43J to 120J with impact velocities of 15m/s to 25m/s. Load-time history data were recorded to characterise the impact properties of the sandwich panels. Numerical models were implemented in LS-Dyna 3D to predict the modes of damage and the results were compared with experimental data. Experimental and numerical approaches were employed by Liu et al. [8] to examine the impact resistance of Nomex honeycomb sandwich structures with thin fibre reinforced polymer face-sheets. A hemispherical steel impactor with a diameter of 12.7 mm and mass of 2.631 kg was utilised in Instron CEAST 9350 drop-weight machine to conduct the experiments. The tests were conducted to probe the effects of impact energy, the face-sheet stacking sequence, and thickness. The finite element analyses of the response of the honeycomb structures subjected to oblique impact numerically were used because such impact experiments were difficult to perform in the experimental testing. The impact resistance and the perforation depth were substantially influenced by the variation in the oblique angle between the impactor and the sandwich structure. Results of both experimental and numerical studies of the low-velocity oblique impact response of composite sandwich panels were reported by Ivanez et al. [9]. The sandwich specimens of size 120×120×12.4 mm were made of carbon-fibre/epoxy face-sheets and Nomex honeycomb core. A CEAST Fractovis 6785 drop-tower testing machine with a hemispherical tip impactor of 20 mm diameter and a total mass of 3.620 kg was utilised to conduct the experimental tests. Four different impact angles i.e. 0°, 5°, 10°, and 15° (the angle between the normal of the sandwich specimen and the axis of the impactor) were employed to perform the oblique impact tests. It is found from the literature that a lot of studies are primarily focused on the single ballistic impact response of sandwich panels without much attention to the effects of multiple impacts. The multiple impacts are standard situations when the projectiles originate from firearms or anti-aircraft missile systems. The perforation of composite sandwich structures with honeycomb core under high-velocity impact tests was discussed by Buitrago et al. [10]. They considered the sandwich specimens composed of carbon/epoxy facesheets and an aluminium honeycomb core. These specimens were subjected to impact using an AIG + gas gun (Sabre Ballistics) and spherical steel projectiles of 1.7 g and 7.5 mm in diameter. The impact velocities recorded were from 92 to 548 m/s. The impact response of the composite structures was analysed using experimental values of residual velocity, ballistic limit, and contact time.

For effective applications of polymer composite structural components, it is essential to predict residual structural response (i.e. load-carrying capability) of ballistically damaged panels. Compression after impact tests (CAI) are normally undertaken to validate damaged structures affected by impact loadings [11-13]. Castanié et al. [14] have scrutinised structural response of sandwich panels composed of graphite-epoxy facesheets and Nomex honeycomb core. Intact and perforated sandwich specimens were tested using compressive loading. It was indicated that the crack in damaged sandwich panels propagates in orthogonal plane during the tests. The recommendation to develop more robust test rig was made to analyse the effect of induced damage on the composite structures.

No studies to this instance reporting the structural performance of the ballistically damaged sandwich structures due to multiple impact were found in literature. It is important to analyse the post-impact response of sandwich panels with multiple perforation due to ballistic impact.

This paper presents experimental results on the effects of multiple ballistic damage on the structural response of composite honeycomb sandwich panels. Sandwich panels made of composite facesheets made of carbon fibre reinforced plastic and the Nomex honeycomb core were subjected to multiple ballistic shots. The multiple perforations were induced to simulate the damage to composite sandwich structures that can be inflicted by fragments of anti-aircraft ammunition, and small firearms etc. Non-intrusive techniques were utilised to analyse the degree and patterns of damage induced. The intact and ballistically damaged sandwich panels were then subjected to in-plane edgewise compression tests to determine the degradation in mechanical performance.

2 SPECIMEN MANUFACTURE

The composite sandwich panels of dimension 150×150×12mm were manufactured with the front and back facesheets made of CF302 carbon fibre pre-preg plies impregnated with VTM 264 resin system, and the AC-NH-4.8-48 Nomex honeycomb core with a thickness of 10mm. The 1mm-thick facesheets composed of four plies with the stacking sequence of $[0^\circ/45^\circ/-45^\circ/90^\circ]$ for the top, and $[90^\circ/-45^\circ/-45^\circ/0^\circ]$ for the bottom facesheets provided a symmetric material layout with regard to the middle surface. VTA260/PK13-313 adhesive film was used to bond the Nomex honeycomb core with the facesheets, see Figure 1.

Figure 1: Layout of the sandwich specimen

The overall time of the curing process performed in the vacuum bagging was 3 hours cycle at the pressure of 0.9 bar. For the first 1-hour step, 2°C per minute ramp was implemented to acquire a temperature of 120°C. The second step included the one-hour curing at 120°C and the third-hour cooling procedure was carried out with a down ramp of 3°C per minute.

3 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.1 Ballistic testing

Ballistic impact experiments were conducted at a shooting range facility. The 500×500×12mm panels with nine 150×150 mm square target areas marked as shown in Figure 2 were clamped on wooden planks with the spring clamping fixtures.

Figure 2: Ballistic impact test set-up

Live projectiles were fired from the shooting station in the experiments. The chronograph recorded values of impact velocities for the .223 Remington (5.56mm), Mauser (6.5mm), and Win .308

(7.62mm) projectiles were 950 m/s, 797 m/s, and 818 m/s, respectively. These velocities are in close accordance with the corresponding values calculated using the Federal Ammunitions Ballistics Calculator [15] for the factory loaded projectiles.

3.2 Damage analysis

Damage assessment conducted for the sandwich panels has shown that the perforations induced by the .223 Remington (5.56mm), Mauser (6.5mm), and Win.308 (7.62mm) projectiles were about 7mm, 9mm, and 11mm in diameter, respectively (see Figure 3). Complete perforations were observed for all the panels. The oblique impacts induced elliptical-shaped perforations in which the facesheets and the core were damaged significantly due to tearing.

Figure 3: Ballistically perforated panels: (a) 5.56 mm projectile; (b) 6.5 mm projectile (c) 7.62 mm projectile

Also, substantial skin delamination caused by the tearing was observed at the edge of the impact zone after bisecting the sample as presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Damaged sandwich panel (a) cross section and (b) delamination and tearing in the damaged skin.

There was no visible debonding found between the honeycomb core and the laminated composite face-sheets. To analyse the damaged sandwich panels without introducing additional damage that could be caused by a cutting tool, the non-intrusive analysis was undertaken using the method of X-ray inspection and computed tomography.

3.3 X-ray inspection

The X-ray scanning was conducted using Amptek Mini X-ray machine with the scanning power of 50KV/ 80 μ A. A 50 x 50 mm area around perforation was scanned for each panel. The X-ray images

have been generated using the image acquisition software Shadow-cam and are shown in Fig. 5. The extensive damage sustained by the facesheets and the core due to the multiple oblique impacts are clearly seen. The assessment observations obtained based on the optical microscopy and discussed in Section 3.2 is further illustrated by X-ray images.

Figure 5: X-ray scan images of the ballistically damaged panels

3.4 Computed tomography

The General Electric v|tome|x micro-focus Computed Tomography (CT) machine was used for non-intrusive analysis of ballistically damaged sandwich panels. The inspection technology utilised 340KV/500W micro-focus X-ray tube with the scan rate of 127 μ m. The damaged samples have been placed on a horizontal platform and were scanned along the three different axes, i.e. in the front, top and right-hand-side directions. The automated scanning X-ray tube employs the Automated Defect Recognition (ADR) algorithm integrated into the phoenix datos|x 3D computed tomography acquisition and reconstruction software. Using this software, the scanned images for the failure assessment of the damaged sandwich panels were generated. Examples of such images generated from CT scans for the panels subjected to oblique impact are shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Cross-section CT scans of sandwich panels ballistically damaged by multiple impacts

3.5 In-plane edgewise compression tests

In-plane edgewise compression tests (CAI) were conducted on intact and damaged panels to assess their load-bearing capacity. The tests were performed using a 100KN-AG Shimadzu Testing Machine equipped with the AC servo motor driven auto-calibrated load cell system SLFL-100KN-AG-11. The TrapeziumX data acquisition software was utilised to generate the load-displacement data at a sampling rate of 100 kHz. Steel clamps were used at the top and bottom ends of a panel of as shown in Fig. 7. The calibration process was performed with the steel clamps subjected to the compressive loading and the calibration file was obtained. This file was further integrated into the data acquisition

software to attain rectified load-displacement history curves for the sandwich panels.

Figure 7: In-plane edgewise compression test set-up (a) front view (b) side view

Three intact and nine ballistically damaged panels (three panels, each subjected to the multiple impacts, for the three different projectiles) were tested under compressive loading. The averaged load-displacement curves acquired from the tests are presented in Fig. 8.

Figure 8: Compressive force-displacement curves for the intact and damaged sandwich panels.

It is found from the graphs shown that the failure loads (peak loads) for the damaged panels are about 48%-56% lower than those observed for the intact sandwich panels. Thus, the load carrying capability of the panels under consideration has been substantially compromised by the damage induced by the multiple ballistic impacts presented in this study. The effects due to the change in projectile diameter didn't affect the load-bearing capacity significantly.

4 CONCLUSION

Effects of ballistic impacts on the residual structural performance of composite honeycomb sandwich panels have been studied in this work. Ballistic tests were conducted using live projectiles of three different calibres. The sample panels were subjected to multiple impacts. Optical microscopy, X-ray inspections, and computer tomography methods have been used to analyse the modes and extent of the damage induced. Structural performance of the intact and ballistically damaged panels has been investigated experimentally using in-plane compression tests. Full penetration was observed for all the projectiles fired and they created elliptical holes on the sandwich specimens. It was seen from the edgewise compression-after-impact tests that the reduction in ultimate failure load was about 45%-60% for the panels subjected to the multiple impacts. It is found from the experimental test results that the structural performance of composite sandwich panels is considerably compromised when the ballistic impact damage is induced.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was supported by the Australian Government Research Training Program Scholarship and Advanced Composite Research Unit at UNSW Canberra. The authors also acknowledge the technical support with the CT scanning provided by Yinghua Testing and Inspection (Shanghai) Co. Ltd.

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